

Oxidation Analysis of Chromium(III) valine Complex using the Catalyst Os (VIII) and the Reagent Hexacyanoferrate (III) ion

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Abstract

The kinetics of the oxidation of Chromium (III) valine (an amino acid metal complex, (CrV) by hexacyanoferrate (III) ion in alkaline medium and catalyst Os(VIII) was studied spectrophotometrically at 420 nm. Analysis of the kinetic result revealed that the rate of oxidation was Zero in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and first order with respect to Os (VIII). The reaction between oxidant and (CrV) in alkaline medium exhibit 6:1 stoichiometry. Ionic strength had a significant effect on the rate. The reaction was investigated at different temperatures. The main products were identified as Chromic acid and 2-methyl-propanal by oxidative melt/colored and spot tests. A plausible mechanism was proposed to explain the results of kinetic studies, reaction stoichiometry and product analysis.

Keywords

Kinetics, oxidation, Chromium (III) valine, Osmium (VIII), hexacyanoferrate (III), complex.

Introduction

Amino acids and their metal complexes are essential in the nutrition of mammals. It has a vital function in organ development, particularly in children. It is also used in pharmacology and medical^{7,19,20}. Since amino acid residues are the main constituents of proteins, the study of its sensitivity towards oxidation opens a new area to understand the mechanism involved in the protein and amino acid modifications⁹. Because of their biological relevance and selectivity toward the oxidant to give diverse products, amino acids and their metal complexes are of tremendous interest for oxidation studies^{9,10,21}. People have been using complexes of copper, iron, chromium, cobalt, and other transition metal ions to stop the growth of dangerous microorganisms for ages^{14,18}.

The osmium tetroxide is the most prevalent substance. It is an extremely potent oxidizing agent. $\text{Trans-OsO}_4(\text{OH})^{3-}$ and $\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{1-}$ are unstable octahedral osmium (VIII) complexes that are formed in alkaline media^{4,5}. As a result, osmium tetroxide has been widely employed as a catalyst or oxidizing agent in the field of chemistry¹².

It has been demonstrated that hexacyanoferrate (III) is an effective oxidant for a broad range of organic substrates due to the CN^- ligands resistance to substitution reactions, which makes outer-sphere electron transfer the favoured oxidation pathway^{5,6}.

The antibacterial properties of transition metal-amino acid complexes have been the subject of much investigation. They have shown promising effects when tested against a range of microorganisms^{1,4}. The antibacterial properties of transition metal-amino acid complexes have been thoroughly investigated. They have shown encouraging results in tests against a range of microorganisms^{14,22,23}. Both the trivalent and hexavalent forms of chromium have biological significance, however the trivalent state is more common¹⁴.

Objective of study

Reflecting the vast range of study in this field, this publication summarizes the key findings and conclusions of several research studies. A notable rise in theoretical and liquid phase research may be seen in the case of the oxidation of metal complexes of amino acids, in addition to the conventional equilibrium and structural investigations.

Review of Literature

Short communication kinetics of chromium(III)-oxidation in topsoil, Outer-sphere hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of organic substrate, Oxidation of salicylaldehyde by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)-kinetics and mechanistic study, Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of L-valine by tributyl ammonium chlorochromate in acidic medium, Kinetics of oxidation of amino acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), Oxidation of organic compounds with osmium tetroxide, Kinetics and mechanism of osmium(VIII)-catalyzed oxidation of phosphite by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium, Osmium(VIII)-catalyzed oxidation of diclofenac sodium by diperiodatoargentate(III) complex in aqueous alkaline medium, Reaction kinetics of sonochemical oxidation of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) in aqueous solutions were studied for this paper. (1,5,6,7,8,9,12,13,16,17). For this study, the kinetics and mechanism of the ruthenium(III)-catalyzed oxidation of L-proline by hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous alkali and the oxidation of L-valine by copper(III) periodate complex in alkaline medium were also studied (19,20). The synthesis and characterization of amino acid metal complexes were also studied (2,3,4,10,11,14,15,18,21,22,23).

Methodology

The following substances were made by E. Merck India Ltd.: oxalic acid, potassium hydroxide, chromium nitrate, phenolphthalein, osmium tetroxide, sodium hydroxide, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, and valine. Hexacyanoferrate (III) of potassium was produced by FlukaPuriss. All of the solutions were prepared using triple-distilled conductivity water in Pyrex glasses.

Preparation of Chromium (III) valine complex [CrV]:

Mix 25 mL of amino acid valine solution with 20 mL of chromium nitrate solution to create the complex, then stir for two hours at 60°C. They created a purple precipitate, cleaned it with ethanol, re-crystallized it in methanol, and kept it in a desiccator^{3,4,11,14,22,23}.

Standardisation of Osmium tetroxide:

A glass tube containing one gram of OsO₄ was taken. It broke into a beaker filled with a solution of 0.5 N sodium hydroxide. The pieces of glass tube were taken out of the solution. Until the substance was completely dissolved, these bits were again cleaned in the same beaker using purified water. The solution was then moved to a measuring flask that held one litre of water. Further, the OsO₄ solution was iodometrically standardized^{10,13}.

λ_{max} of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III):

An Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer (model CL-27) and a double beam BiosyncTecnology Spectrophotometer (model number BST 2800) were used to measure the absorbance of unreacted (0.001M) potassium hexacyanoferrate (III), which would be selected as the oxidant, at various wavelengths. It exhibits λ_{max} (420 nm) for an absorbance vs wavelength graph for potassium hexacyanoferrate (III)^{10,21}.

Molar absorption coefficient of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III):

Potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) has a molar absorbance coefficient of 1000 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 420 nm, which is in conformity with the value that was specified (1030 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)^{17,21}.

Measurement of the rate constants:

A double beam Biosync Tecnology Spectrophotometer (BST 2800) and an Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer (CL-27) have been utilized to measure the absorbance of the

reaction mixture at 420 nm^{17,21}.

The reactions were found to be too sluggish to investigate in alkaline medium without a catalyst. It took around 24 to 36 hours to fully oxidize the chromium (III) valine complex in alkaline medium without a catalyst. Therefore, an Os (VIII) catalyst was added to the reaction mixtures in order to speed up the reactions. Alkaline reactions were found to be nearly complete when an Os (VIII) catalyst was present. The absorbance vs time plots were almost linear for more than two half-lives, suggesting a zero-order interaction with potassium hexacyanoferrate (III). The slope of the absorbance vs time linear plot was determined for each case. The following formula (1) was used to determine the rate constant, k_0 ²¹:

$$\text{Rate Constant } (k_0) = \frac{\text{Slope}}{1000} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1: Zero order plot for the of oxidation of CrV.

The identical process was used in the kinetic study with Os (VIII) as a catalyst.

Stoichiometry of the reactions:

The following two circumstances were used to establish the stoichiometry of the reactions.

[Substrate] >>Oxidant
[Substrate] <<Oxidant

The initial oxidation product of the substrate is provided by experimental condition (i), whereas the entire oxidation process is provided by condition (ii). The [hexacyanoferrate (III)] was measured before to the procedure, and the absorbance at 420 nm was computed until it attained a steady value. We used equation (1) to calculate the amount of unreacted [hexacyanoferrate (III)].

[Hexacyanoferrate (III)] and [substrate] have a stoichiometry ratio of 6:1 for the Chromium (III) valine complex. Consequently, the following is the stoichiometric equation for the oxidation of the Chromium (III) valine complex:

Product Analysis:

The product was tested in two different experimental settings.

[substrate] >> [oxidant]

[substrate] << [oxidant]

The ultimate oxidation products of the substrates are obtained under the experimental condition (b). The Chromium (III) valine complex's main oxidation products were determined to be CrO_3 , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCHO}$, NH_3 , and CO_2 . The oxidative melt/colored test¹⁵ verified the oxidation product CrO_3 . Ammonia was validated with Nessler's reagent¹⁶, 2-methyl-propanal, a carbonyl product, was confirmed using 2, 4-DNP², and CO_2 was qualitatively recognized by passing the released gas through lime water.

Result and Discussion

Order with Respect to Hexacyanoferrate (III):

A combination of constant [substrate], [Os (VIII)], $[\text{OH}^-]$, and ionic strength was used to estimate the reaction order for hexacyanoferrate (III). From 8.0×10^{-4} to 16×10^{-4} , the [hexacyanoferrate (III)] was changed out. Fig. 1 depicts the absorbance vs time plot for the oxidation of Chromium (III) valine in this study, indicating that order was zero in the presence of hexacyanoferrate (III). More evidence for the zero-order process in connection to [hexacyanoferrate (III)] came from the fact that the $t_{1/2}$ values rose as [hexacyanoferrate (III)] climbed but the k_0 values stayed constant with changes in the beginning.

Table 1: Chromium (III) valine oxidation values for k_0 and $t_{1/2}$ at various beginning

[hexacyanoferrate (III)]

Temp. = 308K, $10^2 [\text{CrV}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

$10^5 \text{ Os (VIII)} = 1.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$10^4 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	8.0	10.0	12.0	14.0	16.0
$10^5 k_0$ ($\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	8.1238	7.9957	7.8121	8.717	7.9596
Half life period $t_{1/2}$ (minutes)	4.48	5.65	7.36	9.54	11.47

Dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$:

The graphs of chromium (III) valine between k_0 and $[\text{OH}^-]$ were linear. Fig. 2 shows examples of these charts. The ten-fold change in $[\text{OH}^-]$ of chromium (III) valine was investigated at five different temperatures because higher $[\text{OH}^-]$ was linked to a deviation from zero order behaviour. The findings are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Effect of $[\text{OH}^-]$ on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of Chromium (III) valine.

$10^2 [\text{CrA}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

$10^5 \text{ Os [VIII]} = 1.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$10^2 \text{ [OH]}^- \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$				
	1	3	5	7.5	10
	$10^5 k_0 \text{ (mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$				
303	4.656	8.7859	9.223	11.336	13.927
308	7.237	9.423	10.165	14.837	16.285
313	9.946	12.662	14.331	17.035	18.926
318	14.256	16.953	20.514	25.886	28.826
323	21.897	25.866	28.698	33.586	36.824

Fig. 2: k_0 vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ plots for the oxidation of $[\text{CrV}]$ at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K

Chromium (III) valine's alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation was studied at various $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ while keeping the concentrations of the other reagents constant. The graphs between k_0 and $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ were linear and almost extended to the origin for a ten-fold shift in the initial $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$, as seen in Fig.

3. The oxidation of chromium (III) valine by hexacyanoferrate (III) catalyzed by Os (VIII) has a reaction order of one with regard to $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ in an alkaline medium.

Dependence on $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$

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3. The oxidation of chromium (III) valine by hexacyanoferrate (III) catalyzed by Os (VIII) has a reaction order of one with regard to $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ in an alkaline medium.

The findings of this investigation are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Impact of $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ on the oxidation of chromium (III) valine to hexacyanoferrate (III).

$10^3 [\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\text{CrV}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

$10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$10^5 \text{ Os [VIII]} \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$				
	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	5.0
	$10^5 k_0 \text{ (mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$				
303	1.94	5.98	12.68	15.23	18.46
308	5.28	10.86	18.44	26.88	33.64
313	7.43	17.58	28.35	36.98	57.58
318	8.22	22.86	38.88	51.64	71.68
323	11.12	30.58	45.92	69.64	88.88

Fig. 3: k_0 vs [Os (VIII)] plots for the oxidation of [CrV] at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K

Dependence on [Chromium (III) valine]:

By examining the effects of different [CrV] on the values of k_0 at constant concentrations of all other reagents, the order of the reaction with regard to Chromium (III) valine was ascertained. Ten changes were made to the [substrate] in chromium (III) valine. The plots of k_0^{-1} vs $[CrV]^{-1}$ were found to be linear in each case, with an intercept on the k_0^{-1} axis. Table 4 contains the data, and Fig. 4 shows these charts.

Table 4: $10^4 [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5 Os(VIII) = 1.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

$10^2 [OH^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\mu] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$[CrV]^{-1} (\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3)$				
	1000	500	250	166.66	125
	$10^{-4} k_0^{-1} (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s})$				
303	11.974	8.8039	5.9585	3.1977	2.8699
308	9.9675	5.9791	3.7802	2.7457	3.3481
313	7.6274	5.3075	3.8969	2.2123	1.7819
318	2.6893	1.8989	1.4974	0.9249	0.3272
323	1.274	0.9039	0.4565	0.1977	0.1179

Fig 4: k_0^{-1} vs $[CrV]^{-1}$ plots for the oxidation of Chromium (III) valine at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K.

Effect of the ionic strength:

The ionic strength of a standard sodium chloride solution was altered in order to investigate the effect of ionic strength on the Chromium (III) valine complex. As the ionic strength grew, it was discovered that the k_0 values increased in each case.

Mechanism of oxidation of Chromium (III) valine complex (CrV)^{8,19,20,21}:

It should be noted that the creation of product (1) in the proposed process is demonstrated by Eq (5). As demonstrated by stoichiometry and product analysis in the case of Os (VIII) catalyzed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of Chromium (III) valine complex, product (1) undergoes rapid oxidation under experimental conditions to produce chromic acid, 2-methyl-propanal, a carbonyl compound, carbon dioxide, and ammonia.

Conclusion

Os (VIII) catalyzed the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of the chromium (III) valine complex, which was studied in an alkaline solution from 303 K to 323 K and from 0.01 M to 0.1 M of substrate. When it came to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, the reaction rate was zero, but it was one for Os (VIII). The primary main products of the reactions were the carbonyl compound 2-methyl-propanal and chromic acid. Sodium chloride solutions were used to aid enhance the reaction rate as the ionic strength rose. It was observed that the plot k_0^{-1} vs $[\text{CrV}]^{-1}$ was linear with an intercept on the k_0^{-1} axis in each case.

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